

Protocol

Exploring Degrowth Policy Proposals 2021-2025 to Inform Degrowth Strategy: A systematic map and evidence synthesis relating policy to transition strategies and knowledge gaps

A systematic map update with amendments

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Abstract

Degrowth is a multi-faceted transdisciplinary challenge to capitalist ontological and epistemological paradigms, notably the primary goal of economic growth. Degrowth critiques the environmental and social contradictions of capitalist progress while raising the alarm over the technological fixations that underpin the 'Green Transition' and the 'Sustainable Development Goals'.

Degrowth literature has been subject to systematic reviews that attempt to synthesise the knowledge (Haddaway et al., *forthcoming*), including three reviews within the field of degrowth policy proposals, such as those by Cosme et al. (2017), Parrique (2019) and Fitzpatrick et al. (2022). Since the last systematic mapping degrowth research has substantially increased.

The scope of this project is to address the literature from 2021-2025, as an update with amendments that respond to previous syntheses. It will engage with critics who are concerned that degrowth is retreating to an academic discipline that marginalises Global South voices and demands for justice (e.g. Dengler & Seebacher, 2019; Rodríguez-Labajos 2019; Belmonte-Ureña 2021; Hennen 2022; Al Mahdi 2025).

Furthermore, we make two progressions:

- 1) Synthesising using a conceptual framework that shows the relationship of each proposal to the transition strategies considered relevant to degrowth, presenting them in relation to theories of change and strategic logics.
- 2) Moving from tally counting of policy proposals and making visible those areas that are currently neglected, identifying issues of Eurocentric bias within degrowth scholarship by emphasising knowledge gaps relevant to Global South stakeholders.

Methods

We will systematically map and synthesise degrowth literature for policy proposals using seven databases to identify scholarly articles and grey literature using tailored search strings. Titles, abstracts and keywords will be screened against defined inclusion and exclusion criteria with consistency checking at the outset and at the start of full-text screening. Data will be extracted, coded, stored and synthesised using agreed keywords and themes. Furthermore, policy proposals will be analysed against a conceptual framework that will be developed and inspired by existing frameworks and typologies developed by Demaria et al. (2013), Parrique (2019), Wright (2019), Chertkovskaya (2022), and Hauge & Hickel (2025).

Through a rigorous map of the evidence base, this synthesis will provide a meta-level understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of degrowth strategy by considering the policy proposals relationally to strategic and transformative logics. This review aims to support researchers, policymakers, activists, and specifically critics from the Global South. Our intent is to support work that builds degrowth knowledge

in movements for transformative change through assisting the development of a more coherent political strategy.

1. Background & Research Objectives

Degrowth is a multi-faceted transdisciplinary challenge to capitalist ontological and epistemological paradigms, notably the primary goal of economic growth. Degrowth critiques the environmental and social contradictions of capitalist progress while raising the alarm over the technological fixations that underpin the 'Green Transition' and the 'Sustainable Development Goals'.

Degrowth is frequently described as an emerging discipline that has a grassroots origin, which has expanded into the academic field with increasing research outputs. The evidence to illustrate the increased attention being paid to degrowth ideas includes [the 2023 Beyond Growth Conference](#) hosted by the European Parliament, attendance at the [national degrowth conferences](#) and the success of the book *Capital in the Anthropocene*, selling half a million copies in Japan, which introduced Kohei Saito and his theory of degrowth communism. In June 2025 the [ISEE-Degrowth 2025 Conference in Oslo](#) saw a gathering of 1200 people from 60 countries across most continents and with over 900 presentations that indicated the expanding interest and output covering degrowth concepts, including multiple policy proposals and instruments.

Five years after the publication of Jason Hickel's book *Less is More* (2020) a debate has erupted within the degrowth community, experienced as a tension but offering an opportunity for making degrowth concepts more relevant to this moment of environmental catastrophe, widespread disenfranchisement from 'democratic' politics and policy, and the profound geopolitical violence that manifests in unchallenged genocide, wars, threats of nuclear annihilation and heightened imperial appropriation from Global South countries and people.

This debate has found expression through a series of blog posts on [degrowth.info](#) (Ahern, 2025; Gasparro & Vico, 2025; Liegey et al., 2025) and at [ISEE-Degrowth 2025](#), and has taken two separate but recognisably connected forms. Firstly, as a robust critique of the degrowth movement from the **Delinking & Degrowth Collective** (part of [the International Degrowth Network](#)), who challenge the commitment of the 'movement' to advance Global South Sovereignty through disrupting the Imperial Mode of Living that extracts an Unequal, and Ecologically Unequal, Exchange (Al Mahdi, 2025). Secondly, as frustration at the orientation towards an academic discipline functioning as an epistemic community that meets at

conferences (Hennen, 2022). This is seen as degrowth offering top-down policies (Cosme et al., 2017) using research funds provided by an EU complicit in genocide and wedded to economic growth. Positioning degrowth (back) in **grassroots movement(s)** was emphasised in Oslo where both tensions were summarised by Ekaterina Chertkovskaya during the closing session.

Degrowth has been subject to systematic reviews that attempt to synthesise the knowledge. For example, Haddaway et al. (forthcoming) assess the quality of evidence syntheses in the field by examining the review conduct of over 40 systematic reviews on post-growth and degrowth using the Collaboration for Environmental Evidence Synthesis Appraisal Tool (CEESAT). These include three reviews within the field of degrowth policy proposals: Cosme et al. (2017), Parrique (2019) and Fitzpatrick et al. (2022) that explore the complex, often multilayered, policy solutions presented to address the complex issues that degrowth critiques. However, as Fitzpatrick (2024: 84) says of his work, *“Alas, the study served as a coherence check rather than a political strategy for the movement”*.

It is crucial to define what is meant by ‘policy’ in this project. Parrique (2019) in his analysis uses the definition of a policy as *‘a course of principle of action adopted or proposed by an organisation or individual’*, adding that the crucial part of this action or principle is that it has to be **intentional**, meaning that it has to have a certain goal and want to achieve something. Furthermore, the difference between policy and policy proposals is solely that until one policy is implemented or enacted, it’s still a proposal.

The biggest advantage of such a broad definition is that it allows it to see anyone as a potential policymaker. This kind of approach is very well aligned with a degrowth vision of horizontal governance models, which include the diversity of actors.

In that sense, degrowth policy is a course or principle of action adopted or proposed by an organisation or individual aiming to achieve the objectives of degrowth (Parrique, 2019).

Since the last systematic mapping and analysis of degrowth policy proposals done by Fitzpatrick et al. (2022) degrowth research has constantly increased. While the authors had intended to produce yearly updates to the work completed in 2020, this has not happened, which has left 5 years of new texts to be read, analysed and coded.

This is the scope of this project, and it is work that is intended as both an update and a progression of the work published by Fitzpatrick et al. (2022). That work established a detailed and comprehensive inventory of degrowth proposals up to 2020, which indicated how the identified policies fit into policy design and transition strategies by addressing five key issues of precision, frequency, visibility, diversity, and interactions. This work has contributed to two communications platforms – [The Degrowth Database](#) by JP Arellano and [Degrowth \(Policies\) Demystified](#) by Sara Al Mahdi.

Our update will undertake to replicate the study through reviewing the literature picking up from where Fitzpatrick et al. (2022) left off.

- **The first research objective will be to identify, code, analyse and synthesise all literature (journal articles, books, book chapters, student theses, grey literature) published in the period from 2021 to 2025 that includes degrowth policy proposals.**

Previous syntheses categorised policy proposals by theme. The latest by Fitzpatrick et al. (2022) grouped policy proposals into 13 themes: food, education and culture, energy and environment, geopolitics and governance, indicators, inequality, finance, production and consumption, science and technology, trade, tourism, urban planning and work. The themes will be adjusted due to changing emphases in degrowth research, as a consequence of external/critical voices, and rapidly changing geopolitical situations.

Furthermore, we recognise that the degrowth transition is complicated by positive and negative synergies between policies. These synergies arise from diverse economic, cultural, geographic, and temporal landscapes. As a result, issues of scale, democracy, and impact are important for acceptance by diverse actors. In that sense policy proposals can become meaningless if detached from both a theory of change and transition strategies.

- **Our second research objective is to offer a conceptual framework. It will organise the coded policies, recognising the categorisations that are already being suggested. We will also consider some existing frameworks and/or typologies. For an overview see Table 1.**

Producing a conceptual frame will allow us to consider whether the policy proposals presented operate within a ‘coherent theory of transition’ that addresses issues of state, power and the balance of forces

that can be used to confront vested interests, that maintain capitalism and are positioned to resist anticapitalist transformative change, and increasingly forcefully when the challenge is successful and when presented by frontline communities, particularly in the Global South.

We will use this to see if this work could inform strategies, allowing for degrowth ideas to find greater expression in social movements, and help to inform understanding of why degrowth policies have not been fully implemented. This meta-level understanding aims to move away from cataloguing policy proposals to presenting them in relation to theories of change and strategic logics capable of establishing societal transformation (Kommandeur et al., 2025; Stevenson, 2025). Ultimately, the goal is to categorise existing degrowth policy proposals according to their relative importance regarding the spheres of change and different strategic transformations, which will help to understand the responsibility of actors at all levels, identify potential pushbacks and trade-offs when implementing policies but also identify the risk of co-optation when considering policy proposals. In this way, we will approach all policy proposals as having a potential role to play in a ‘biodiversity of resistance’ – drawing upon the word ‘ecosystem’ as used by Davis et al. (2022: xi):

“to avoid a reifying framework and to amplify a dynamic ecology of political work ... to mark the complexity of a landscape populated with intertwined networks, campaigns, mobilisations, and organisations ... but also provides key imaginative and conceptual tools to deal with our contemporary moment” .

Table 1 A few identified frameworks and/or typologies relevant for policy discussions in degrowth

Author(s)	Name of framework or typology	Types
Wright (2010)	Strategic transformation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ruptural transformation ● Interstitial transformation ● Symbiotic transformation
Demaria et al. (2013)	Degrowth strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Oppositional activism ● Political proposals ● Building of alternatives
Parrique (2019)	Matrix for understanding degrowth policy proposals	Combines three ideal types from Demaria et al. (2013) with four spheres of change: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Individuals at the household level ● Associations at the community level ● Buyers and sellers at the market level

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Public servants and elected representatives at the government or state level
Wright (2019)	Strategic logics for anticapitalism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Smashing capitalism ● Dismantling capitalism ● Taming capitalism ● Resisting capitalism ● Escaping capitalism
Chertkovskaya (2022)	A strategic canvas for degrowth	<p>Adds two more categories to those of Wright (2019):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Building alternatives ● Halting
Hauge and Hickel (2025)	A progressive framework for green industrial policy	<p>Identifies three policy areas and connects them to policy instruments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scale down ecologically harmful industries ● Organise production more around public benefit ● Global ecological justice

Finally, this synthesis of degrowth policy proposals can be used to identify gaps and underrepresentation in degrowth research of geopolitical issues, which are needed to make clearer the connection between degrowth in the Global North, which is a path towards dismantling the systems of accumulation, and the liberation of the Global South (Magalhães Teixeira, 2024). Notably, the issues that are concerned with global convergence, including issues of debt, reparations, loss and damage, just transitions, human rights, war and the military industrial complex, migration and displacement. The existing themes do not render these issues visible, and that may perpetuate diminished attention. If a proposal is relatively invisible, it is important to ask why. What is needed to highlight research areas for degrowth scholars?

- **The third aim of this project will be to identify policy areas that are not being addressed, not addressed in enough detail, and therefore to render the invisible visible.**

Despite the large number of degrowth policy proposals presented, the policies/strategies have been described as:

“vague, patchy, messy, rigid, loose, and abstract – that is, not good enough for application... proposed policies are poorly designed and have as such failed to convince any decision-maker” (Parrique, 2019: 500).

At worst imprecision and unwillingness to confront and nail-down harsh realities, capitalism, imperialism, state, and power leave degrowth poorly positioned to centre a globally equitable and reparative future of sufficiency for all even though it is frequently described within the degrowth message.

This is particularly important in order for addressing issues of Eurocentric bias within degrowth scholarship by emphasising knowledge gaps relevant to Global South stakeholders. Working with stakeholders in this debate, we will focus attention on knowledge gaps that make degrowth and environmental justice in the Global South a *'not so natural alliance'* (Rodríguez-Labajos et al., 2019).

Degrowth cannot claim innocence based upon it being 'an emerging discipline'; it has come of age and must accept the responsibility of maturity. We will hold to account research that does not help progress the knowledge into praxis that can inform strategy, challenge power and lead to transformative change. Degrowth must urgently escape the academy and become a player in movements confronting systems that threaten civilisation and planetary spheres. It needs to do so by understanding the current state of policy research and presenting a map outlining the responses that degrowth can offer to confronting the metacrisis.

A series of blogs on [the degrowth.info platform](https://the-degrowth.info) have brought the attention of the entire community to the discussion, creating a Zeitgeist at this moment when we are updating the presentation of degrowth policy proposals that have been offered since the last review that concluded in 2020. As if to confirm the importance of this work, the [12th International Degrowth Conference August 2027](https://www.degrowth.info/en/12th-international-degrowth-conference-august-2027) is themed: Policy, Practice and Culture to "celebrate the decolonial momentum of the just transition"

2. Stakeholder Engagement

The stakeholders will be the researchers who will conduct the review and the synthesis. Throughout this process, we will also interact and coordinate with the authors of previous systematic reviews of degrowth policies to ensure synergies and that lessons learned from previous work are integrated within our work.

Particularly important for the third aim of this paper is our plan to be informed by *The Degrowth and Delinking Collective* over issues raised at the Degrowth Conferences (Pontevedra 2024 and Oslo 2025) regarding Eurocentric bias within degrowth.

3. Methods

Systematic reviews aim to provide a gold standard in summarising and synthesising documented evidence, including knowledge clusters as well as gaps. While such reviews are common in health, often focused upon quantitative data, providing a gold standard reporting methodology for narrative or qualitative methods has been unable to rely on the same protocols, leading to substandard reporting (Haddaway et al., 2017, 2018). The response has been the development of RepORting standards for Systematic Evidence Syntheses (ROSES), a reporting protocol that addresses this issue with respect to the environment, which makes it applicable to reviewing policy evidence in the degrowth field. The protocol is considered together with the Collaboration for Environmental Evidence (CEE) Guidelines¹, in order to allow a high standard mapping to be conducted, which increases transparency through the initial stages up to synthesis (Haddaway et al., 2018).

The ROSES map protocol involves a step-by-step process that we will follow. This process establishes comprehensiveness, transparency, repeatability and objectivity through adhering to the following guidelines (Haddaway et al., 2017):

- Described in sufficient detail to allow full repeatability and traceability,
- Follow a systematic approach to identifying and screening relevant academic and grey literature,
- Show critical appraisal of the validity.

Our mapping will be guided by the ROSES methodology (Haddaway et al., 2018), using the methodology for systematic map protocols, which addresses the reliability of mapping exercises and ensures that it adheres to recognised standards, in particular the CEE Guidelines. We aim for transparent reporting to strengthen the utility of the findings.

We are presenting a methodology that divides the work into seven key stages:

¹ Established 2008 as the coordinating body supporting work in conservation and environmental management similar to the work of Cochrane in biomedical science.

1. Develop a Search Protocol
2. Conducting Search
3. Retrieving Papers
4. Screening – Title and Abstract Review
5. Screening – Full Text Review
6. Coding
7. Synthesis

3.1. Conducting searches

3.1.1. Bibliographic databases and languages

We will search the following bibliographic databases for relevant records using 39 known translations of “degrowth” using the search string outlined below. For each database, the string will be adapted to the syntax required by that database:

Table 2 Bibliographic databases that will be searched with the known translations of “degrowth”

Database	Notes
Web of Science Core Collections (1970-Present)	Including the following indexes: Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI), Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-EXPANDED), Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI), Arts & Humanities Citation Index (A&HCI), Conference Proceedings Citation Index – Science (CPCI-S), Conference Proceedings Citation Index – Social Science & Humanities (CPCI-SSH), Book Citation Index – Social Sciences & Humanities (BKCI-SSH), Book Citation Index – Science (BKCI-S)
Scopus	
The Lens Scholarly search	Including the following indexes: Microsoft Academic Graph, CrossRef, CORE, OpenAlex, PubMed, PubMedCentral (https://www.lens.org)
Google Scholar	Via Publish or Perish, supporting export of the first 1000 records displayed.

	Searches will be repeated to include “allintitle:” to conduct an additional search restricting to title words.
ProQuest Dissertations and Theses	Via ProQuest
Preprint servers	SSRN, rXiv, agriRxiv, SocArXiv, ArXiv

3.1.2. Search strings

We will search the above bibliographic databases using a bespoke adaptation of the following Boolean search string, formatted to Web of Science. We will search across the title (TI), abstract (AB), and author-provided keyword (AK) fields. We will look for literature published in the period between 1 January 2021 and 10 August 2025 using the 39 known translations of the word “degrowth” from Fitzpatrick (2025).

Table 3 Search string to be used in bibliographic databases, including the provisional hits on Scopus on 08/08/2025

String number	String text	Provisional hits
Degrowth translations (in title, abstract, keywords, and field of study)	“degrowth OR “de growth” OR “de-growth” OR “عربي عربانخفاض النم” OR “desazkundea” OR “gutxitu” OR “decreixment” OR “去增长” OR “odrast” OR “nerŭst” OR “modvækst” OR “ontgroei” OR “tasaareng” OR “kasvun” OR “kohtuutalous” OR “décroissance” OR “decrecimiento” OR “entwachstum” OR “postwachstum” OR “αποανάπτυξη” OR “חוסר צמיחה” OR “nemnövekedés” OR “decrescita” OR “脱成長” OR “デグロース” OR “탈성장” OR “neaugsmé” OR “rimšana” OR “veksfri utvikling” OR “dewzrost” OR “decrecimiento” OR “Дерост” OR “odrast” OR “bezrastová” OR “Degresija” OR “decrecimiento” OR “kupungua” OR “nerväxt” OR “küçülme” OR “антизростання”	8,342

3.1.3. Web-based search engines

The search strings for Google Scholar will be simplified to account for its basic search functionality as follows:

1. “degrowth” OR “de growth” OR “de-growth” OR “décroissance” OR “decrecimiento” OR “decrecimiento”
2. allintitle:degrowth OR “de growth” OR “de-growth” OR “décroissance” OR “decrecimiento” OR “decrecimiento”

We will perform the searches in the software [Publish or Perish](#), allowing the first 980-1000 search results to be exported as an RIS file that can then be added to bibliographic database results prior to deduplication and then screening.

3.1.4. Grey literature

We will include relevant grey literature in our synthesis by searching web-based academic search engines such as Google Scholar - recognised for effectively cataloguing grey literature (Haddaway et al., 2020; Haddaway & Bayliss, 2015), as well as preprint servers and repositories like ProQuest Dissertations and Theses. Furthermore, in case not captured during the initial literature search, we will include relevant publications coming from non-governmental organisations and civil society that we are aware of.

This approach is particularly important for the degrowth discourse, where many contributors are activists, early-career academics, and practitioners who often face barriers to publishing in peer-reviewed journals due to limited time, funding, or institutional support. By including grey literature, we aim to ensure a more comprehensive and inclusive synthesis that reflects the full spectrum of voices within the field.

3.1.5. Estimating the comprehensiveness of the search

A large number of databases are being consulted, increased to seven from the four used for the previous policy review. This is expected to increase the chance of finding the relevant material, including grey literature. At the start some revised string searches will be used to test whether the data capture is

relevant. The large number of papers that are predicted to be obtained makes comprehensiveness more certain than a review that is only anticipated to find a small number of studies.

3.1.6. Search Update

The search strings will be tested at the start - when these are considered suitable, there will be no plans to update the search due to the limits of time.

3.2. Article screening, study inclusion and exclusion criteria

3.2.1. Screening strategy

Preparing the References for Screening

References will be imported using the following criteria:

1. All fields for export option will be checked
2. If this is not possible the Reference (citation), Abstract, and DOI link will be exported.

The number of references from each source will be recorded.

Duplicates and De-duplication

The removal of duplicates will precede screening.

De-duplication will be conducted manually and with automation tools ([Zotero](#) and [Covidence](#)).

There will be separate records kept of the number of studies removed manually and by automation.

Where confidence in the automation tools is low there will be manual checks conducted and there will be a final manual check prior to the screening phase.

3.2.2. Screening

The screening will take place between the literature search and the data extraction. It is to be carried out in two phases:

- 1) Title, abstract and keyword screen.
- 2) Full-text screen.

There will be three reviewers (One Lead = NF and Two Principals = AMR and CD) for both phases of the screening process.

Considering the large amount of materials that will be screened, we will use [Covidence software](#) and [Zotero](#) during both screening phases.

First phase screening: Title, abstract and keywords

This part of the review will identify and remove irrelevant studies and identify potentially relevant studies. It will follow a **one-step screen** in which the title, abstract and, where relevant, keywords are screened together.

A **single-reviewer** screen will be conducted to optimise resources but with **proportional screening** of 10% of studies at each stage to ensure consistency and reduce personal bias among reviewers – see consistency checking below.

Managing **texts without abstracts** – these include books, book chapters, and theses. The book contents, chapter headings, chapter subheadings, preface, introduction, index will be scanned for degrowth policy proposals before deciding to include full-text reading.

All articles in Croatian, Serbian or Bosnian to be screened by AMR. All other foreign language (non-English) texts will be translated with online translators (DeepL, Google Translate, <https://www.onlinedoctranslator.com/en/>)

The first guiding question for inclusion of the study to phase one screen is:

Does this study focus on degrowth in the context of ecological sustainability and social equity?

The question is to ensure that papers that use these terms in another way to the focus of the study are not included. Asking this question allows aspects of degrowth that are concerned with equity and social justice to be included.

The studies will be **categorised** for the inclusion in the full-text review using the following terms:

Yes Include in full-text screen

No Exclude from full-text screen

Maybe If unsure or unclear then the issue of inclusion will be resolved with the second principal reviewer, by email/video discussion, and if still uncertain then the issue will be resolved using the lead reviewer as arbiter.

Second phase screening: **Full-Text Screening**

Training on the inclusion and exclusion criteria will occur with a meeting between all reviewers (NF, AMR, CD).

A full PDF of each study must be obtained prior to its review. This will be done through:

- The use of automated software (Covidence, Zotero)
- University library systems
- Writing to authors (where the above fail)

Unobtainable Publications - There will be a separate record, saved on an Excel sheet, of all publications that were unable to be obtained.

The purpose is to screen all relevant studies for degrowth policy proposals and is to be conducted by the two principal reviewers. It will be directed by the original guiding question and supplementary questions:

1. Does the study contain any degrowth policy proposals for achieving the goal of degrowth (listed inclusions below)?
2. Does the study contain policy proposals that relate to the Global South?
3. Does the study contain policy proposals that relate to geopolitical issues (listed below)?

At this stage data extraction and coding will take place so that the process is efficient with respect to time.

Excluded texts will be recorded with reasons for exclusion from the process of data extraction and excluded using the **hierarchy** of reasons established between the reviewers.

Records To Record on Excel for PRISMA Flow

1. Total Studies at Search Phase: Articles, Books, Book Chapters, Grey Literature
2. Studies excluded at abstract phase with reason
3. Duplicates removed
4. Studies not retrieved
5. Studies included for full-text screen
6. Studies included for data extraction and coding
7. Studies excluded at full-text phase with reason

3.2.3. Consistency checking

Inter-Rater Reliability (IRR) is the measure of consistency and agreement between two or more reviewers. This will be measured using the **Kappa statistic** to test-agreement level (McHugh, 2012). This is important because a qualitative study does not require independent screening, therefore, consistency of the individual reviewers in avoiding selection bias is needed for increasing rigour and offering the review higher credibility.

A proportional screen of 10% of studies will be conducted at the start of screening as a blinding trial. This will involve 10% of texts being screened by the Lead reviewer and the two principal reviewers independently. All discrepancies will be discussed with respect to the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

The remaining studies will then be screened by the two principal reviewers if the IRR is high, but where the Kappa score falls below 0.6, or where there is concern over a reviewer's understanding, there will be training and a repeat of the exercise with another 10% of texts screened.

The same procedure will be followed at the full-text screen before continuation with full data extraction by comparing extracted data from 10% of studies referencing the table of inclusion and exclusion required. The results will be compared and methodological changes discussed and recorded if necessary. If the consensus is poor, this will require training and a repeat of the process.

The final report will record the consistency checking activities undertaken.

Conflict Resolution

Where there is disagreement, the method for resolving conflict will depend upon whether there is:

Difference in Vote Aim to resolve through discussion between the reviewers, and by a binding decision by the lead reviewer if unable to resolve.

Difference in Reason The inclusion and exclusion criteria will have an **agreed hierarchy** that will be used to exclude. There can only be one reason therefore the one that is ranked higher by hierarchy will be the one used.

3.2.4. Inclusion criteria

The boundaries of inclusion are intended to ensure that only relevant and high-quality studies that respond to primary and secondary research questions (laid out previously), are included.

The **population** considered are articles that focus on degrowth as defined:

Degrowth – is the downscaling of production and consumption to reduce ecological footprints, planned democratically in a way that is equitable while securing wellbeing (Parrique, 2025).

Study Design – a systematic map that aims to comprehensively summarise the state of the literature.

Intervention – the literature will be screened with respect to identification and recording of policy proposals.

Degrowth Policy and Policy Proposal will be defined as *an intentional course or principle of action adopted or proposed by an organisation or individual aiming to achieve the objective of degrowth, through additive or subtractive changes with the aim to change something, and which exist as proposals until enacted* (Parrique, 2019).

Timeframe are articles published between 01/01/2021 and 01/08/2025.

Publication types are peer-reviewed academic papers, and theses, books, book chapters and relevant grey literature coming from non-governmental organisations and think-tanks.

Languages – see previous 16 translations of the three keywords.

All included publications will be **recorded** on an Excel Sheet and numbers recorded.

3.2.5. Exclusion Criteria

Studies that do not meet the following criteria will be rejected at both the abstract and full read phases of the project.

Criteria for Rejection at Title/Abstract/Keyword Screen

1. Wrong Population - Non-Related Topic
2. Does not mention degrowth in the abstract or keywords
3. Wrong use of degrowth
4. Duplicate
5. Wrong Year

All Excluded publications will be **recorded** on an Excel Sheet and numbers recorded.

Criteria for Rejection at Full-Read Screen

1. No policy proposals
2. Uses the terms only as keywords without discussion
3. Rejects the terms in favour of other positions eg buen vivir, a-growth, donut ...
4. Uses the terms in the wrong context (not related to the definition provided)
5. Only refers to scholars associated with the terms and not the theory/practice
6. Discusses other concepts but without relation to degrowth e.g. circular economy, steady-state
7. The terms do not appear in the full text, only in the abstract

All Excluded publications will be **recorded** on an Excel Sheet and numbers recorded.

Other

1. Rejection of all texts that are **unavailable** at the text retrieval stage. These will be handled separately and an Excel sheet created that lists all unavailable texts. There will be a record of steps taken to retrieve texts at the point of exclusion.

2. Duplicates will be rejected and these will be recorded on a separate Excel sheet.

A PRISMA flow chart will be created for all included and excluded texts and the information will be made available in Supplementary Appendices.

4. Critical appraisal

As outlined in our research objectives, we aim to categorise the identified policy proposals according to the specific policy topics they address. To guide this process, we will draw inspiration from the categorisation developed by Fitzpatrick et al. (2022), assessing its relevance and making adjustments if necessary. In addition, we will map the identified policy proposals using a conceptual framework that we intend to develop. This framework will be grounded in the theories of social change presented in Table 1. above.

5. Data extraction

We will extract a predetermined set of data from each included full text. For data categories see Table 3.

Table 4 Categories of data to be extracted from full texts

Field	Description
Citation	Authors, year, title, journal/source, volume, pages, DOI
Abstract and keywords	
Document type	E.g. article, book, book chapter, thesis, report
Author affiliations	Affiliations of all authors
Policy proposals	An extract of the stated policy proposals
Theoretical framework	Example may include ecological economics, political ecology, sustainability transitions, green growth, ecomodernism, etc.

Conceptual definitions	Definitions of degrowth, post-growth, ecological economics, etc.
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Furthermore, if the text is going through a second phase (full text) screen, it will be further coded by theme, comprehensiveness of proposal, and our conceptual framework. For this we will use a set of keywords, inspired by the keywords used by Fitzpatrick et al. (2022) in their latest systematic review of degrowth policies. A preliminary list of keywords can be seen under Supplementary information. These will be adjusted throughout the coding process as needed and stakeholders. The full list of keywords and coding sheets will be shared once the research is published.

6. Data synthesis and presentation

6.1. Narrative synthesis strategy

The findings from multiple qualitative studies will be integrated using a thematic analysis that identifies key messages and themes from individual studies and connects them to explain the topic as a whole, and which *“is presented as a tried and tested method that preserves an explicit and transparent link between conclusions and the text of primary studies”* (Thomas & Harden, 2008).

We will identify and extract policy proposals using Zotero, Excel and [Atlas.ti](#). The thematic synthesis will involve translation of the concepts, which is recognition of knowledge clusters even when expressed differently, with the purpose of going beyond individual studies to produce a higher-order framework that can offer interpretation, explanation and hypotheses to inform degrowth praxis.

For simplicity the data will be grouped, using and expanding upon the 13 themes developed by Fitzpatrick et al (2022) and not being bound by those themes. Themes will be allowed to emerge during screening and will be populated with ‘data’ established by a process of coding.

6.2. Coding

We will use the keyword codes developed by Fitzpatrick et al. (2022), which will be subject to further development and augmented by codes that will be developed alongside the **conceptual framework**.

Coding will take place line-by-line where relevant policy proposals are offered with the purpose of making the translation of concepts from one study to another possible despite different words being used to describe the concept. Furthermore, [Atlas.ti](#) will be used to identify links between different themes and to visualise the progression of how different themes have been included over the period of 2021-2025. [Atlas.ti](#) will also allow for these links to be visualised and help identify further gaps in research and areas where policy proposals for degrowth are lacking, especially when it comes to the delinking and Global South issues.

Data will be inputted onto an Excel spreadsheet and will be provided as a supplementary appendix. The database will be shared with [the Degrowth Database](#) and [Degrowth \(policies\) Demystified communications tool](#). There will be a clear separation between the 'data-driven' descriptive themes and the 'theory-driven' analytical themes that will be explored in the final synthesis which allows a meta-level analysis to be presented.

6.3. Final Synthesis – Development of an Analytical Frame

The ultimate purpose of the synthesis is to contribute evidence that can inform the future direction of degrowth research and strategy for achieving transformation. The use of the Conceptual Framework will inform the synthesis and interpretation and will be used by all reviewers to provide greater validity to the judgement of the reviewers and mitigate for individual subjectivity. All reviewers will check consistency at the synthesis stage.

6.4. Dissemination of findings

At the conclusion of our study, we strive to create a scholarly article for publication in an appropriate academic periodical. To further expand its reach beyond the academic community, we are committed to promoting this paper to a broader audience, thereby contributing to its impact and relevance. To this end, we plan to submit the findings of our study to current digital repositories. Finally, we intend to present

our results at relevant conferences and gatherings, engaging in dialogue with various stakeholders involved in the degrowth movement.

7. Knowledge gap and cluster

A systematic map “*collates, describes, and catalogues available evidence*” in order to “*identify evidence for policy-relevant questions, knowledge gaps, [...], and knowledge clusters*” (Callaghan et al., 2024).

While synthesising identified policy proposals and facilitated by our conceptual framework, we will emphasise knowledge gaps, particularly where we find a continuation of the same gaps from the previous systematic reviews. Furthermore, we aim to give particular attention to analysing if the gap in degrowth research on the topics of delinking and Global North and Global South connection is being addressed, to identify areas where this is still lacking and call for action. While this may be an uncomfortable realisation for some proponents of degrowth (for an example, see Parrique (2025)). If degrowth proponents are serious about creating transformative strategies, then it is necessary to address reasons why some proposals are not being given satisfactory exposure.

8. Demonstrating procedural independence

No author will make decisions regarding their own work or that of immediate colleagues, where such studies are found the reviewer will record the text has been passed to another reviewer to screen.

9. Declarations

Ana Miljanović Rusan Principal Reviewer

I have no financial competing interest. This work has been completed without dedicated funding, as part of the master's degree in Degrowth: Ecology, Economics and Policy.

Ci Davis Principal Reviewer

I have no financial or non-financial competing interest. This work has been completed without dedicated funding. There are no competing interests other than family and the pressure of paid employment.

Nick Fitzpatrick Lead Reviewer

I have no competing interests. This work has been completed without dedicated funding.

Availability of data and materials:

All data relevant to the preparation of the manuscript will be provided in supplementary files alongside the publication.

Authors' contributions will be determined using the CReDIT author statement at the end of the project.

Supplementary Information

For Calculation of Kappa Statistic

<https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/how-to-calculate-cohens-kappa-in-a-systematic-reviewpdf/265592407>

Listed Inclusion of Policy Proposals that are Degrowth Related

Combining Parrique's 2025 definition of degrowth and Hauge & Hikel conceptual framework

Downscaling of Production

Downscaling of Consumption

Downscaling of Ecologically Harmful Industry

Downscaling Energy Use

Reduction of Ecological Footprints

Practice Democratic Planning

Organise Production for the Public Benefit

Global Ecological Justice

Global Social Justice

Securing Personal Wellbeing

Securing 'ecological policy space' for the Global South

Indicative list of keywords used for coding

Agriculture & Food

agroecology, community garden, community-supported agriculture, food networks, food security, food sovereignty, genetically modified, GMO, herbicides, indigenous, land rights, meat, monoculture, organic, peasant, permaculture, pesticides, plant-based, reforestation, regenerative, relocalise, seasonal, seed bank, self-sufficiency, subsistence, traditional knowledge, urban garden, vegan, vegetarian

Education & Culture

autonomy, community, communities, critical realism, critical thinking, culture, ecofeminist, education, education for sustainable degrowth, education for sustainable development, ESD, epistemology,

feminism, indigenous, local communities, pedagogy, practice, practice theory, praxis, reciprocity, relational goods, self-limitation, sustainability, traditional knowledge, voluntary simplicity

Energy & Environment

abandon, ban, biodiversity, biomass, cap, cap-and-trade, coal, community renewable energy, conservation, deforestation, divest, efficiency, emissions, extraction, fossil fuels, gas, hydro, metals, mining, moratoria, moratorium, mother nature, nature, negative emission technologies, NETs, nuclear, oil, phase out, preservation, prosumer, quotas, reform, regulate, regulation, renewables, resource use, rights to nature, self-consumption, self-production, solar, tax, wind

Geopolitics & Governance

budget, citizen assemblies, colonial, commission, community, convention, decentralize, decision-making, democratic, direct democracy, ecological unequal exchange, eco-social, exploit, forums, government, green new deal, household, imperialism, independence, lobby, mandate, market, military, military-industrial, movements, participatory budgeting, referendum, reform, state, weapons

Housing & Regional Planning

affordable, cities, co-housing, diversity, eco-housing, eco-village, expropriation, guerrilla garden, land, mortgage, occupy, ownership, place, planning, private property, property, renovate, rent, retrofit, social, squat, superblock, shared, space, standards, time, urban garden, urbanism

Indicators

alternative indicators, ecological footprint, eudaemonic, Gini coefficient, GINI, gross domestic product (GDP), gross national happiness, GNH, happiness, hedonic, human needs, objective, postcolonial, post-development, subjective, sufficiency, wellbeing

Inequality

capital accumulation, capital gains, corporate, carbon debt, class, climate debt, distribution, ecological debt, environmental justice, income, inequality, inheritance, intergenerational, intragenerational, maximum, minimum, poverty, pre-distribution, redistribution, wealth

International Trade & Tourism

aviation, cruise, deal, exports, human rights, imports, incentive, industry, international law, limit, regulate, right to live, right to travel, shipping, supply chain, tourism, trade, trade agreement, United Nations World Tourism Organization, UNWTO, value chain, World Trade Organization, WTO

Money, Banking & Finance

complimentary currency, credit, debt, ethical finance, full reserve banking, global tax, growth imperative, impact assessment, inflation, interest, interest rates, International Monetary Fund, IMF, investment, loans, local exchange systems, money, negative income, sovereign, tax avoidance, tax evasion, tax haven, transaction, World Bank

Population

birth rate, contraception, empowerment, family planning, migration, sex education

Production & Consumption (includes waste)

advertisement, advertising, anticapitalist, artisanship, bike kitchen, boycott, business, capitalist mode of production, community-owned, consumption, cooperatives, co-operatives, corporations, decentralisation, design local manufacture local, DGML, digital commons, direct democracy, do-it-yourself, DIY, economic democracy, exchange, fair, firm, gift, hackerspaces, hierarchies, hierarchy, labelling, landfill, luxury products, makerspaces, means of production, micro-factories, monopolies, non-capitalist, non-market, non-for-profit, non-profit, obsolescence, open source, small-scale, life cycle assessment, peer-based production, peer-to-peer production, P2P, production, prosumer, repair, sanction, self-consumption, self-production, sharing, social enterprise, re-localization, repair café, rent, rent-for-free, town meetings, transnational, waste, working bees

Public Services & Facilities

care, childcare, decentralize, decommodification, electricity, energy, health, heating, infrastructure, investment, nationalise, library, public services, social security, utilities, water

Science & Technology

convivial, frugal, funding, innovation, low-tech, nanotechnology, patents, precautionary principle, research, science, technology, technologies, weapons

Transport

airport, aviation, biking, biofuel, bus, car, car-free, cargo, cycling, fuel, harbour, high-speed, hydrogen, kerosene, pathway, petroleum, planes, road, shipping, slow, train, tram

Work

basic income, basic services, care, employ, job guarantee, just transition, informal, labor, leisure, reallocate, redistribute, reduce, reproduction, rest, sharing, shorter, simple way, timebank, unemployment, universal autonomy allowance, UAA, universal basic income, UBI, universal basic services, UBS, unpaid, wage, work time reduction, voluntary simplicity, volunteer

Geopolitics

Human Rights, Debt, Reparations, Food Sovereignty, Energy Sovereignty, Migration, Borders, Abolition, Imperialism, Colonialism, Neocolonialism, Coloniality, Policing, Surveillance, Military, Weapons, Arms, War, Conflict, Violence

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